

Microwave confocal image for the localization of lung cancer

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Abstract: Lung cancer is one of the most common causes of cancer-related death. Once detected it is usually removed through thoracoscopic surgery. However, during the surgery, since the lung deflates a new localization of the nodule is necessary. We suggest combining microwave imaging with a laparoscopic instrument to relocate the tumor during the surgery. In this contribution, a numerical analysis was undertaken to investigate the main parameters affecting microwave imaging such as frequency band, and depth of the nodule. It was found that at 600 MHz a nodule of 1 cm in radius could be imaged up to 10 cm of depth in the lung.

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I. Introduction

Lung cancer represents the most commonly diagnosed cancer type most diagnosed worldwide [1], with a 5-year survival rate of less than one in five [2].

Pulmonary nodules are usually detected incidentally by low-dose helical computed tomography (CT) [3]. In high-risk smokers, solitary pulmonary nodules have a prevalence of 50 % in lung cancer screening and in the case of solid or subsolid form and shape larger than 8 mm they are biopsied or surgically removed for diagnosis [3]. This removal is preferentially performed by video-assisted thoracoscopic surgery (VATS).

A procedure to mark the position of the cancer is necessary before VATS because, at thorax opening, the lung collapses making the previous CT images unreliable for the resection.

Microwave imaging is a suitable solution to locate the tumor also when the lung is collapsed. It was initially proposed for medical use in the detection of breast cancer [4]. It is based on the same principle as radar (**RA**dio **D**etection **A**nd **R**anging) in which an antenna emits electromagnetic wave in the microwave range. When these waves encounter a discontinuity in dielectric properties, such as an object or a lesion, they are partially reflected back toward the antenna. From the intensity and delay of the reflected waves it is possible to obtain information regarding the position of the discontinuity.

An image is produced from the reflected waves in a procedure known as confocal imaging. These images give qualitative information regarding the morphology of the irradiated tissue and can display the approximated position of a tumor. Moreover, a small set of antennas could be embedded in a laparoscopic instrument to automatically produce view-through images of the surrounding tissues.

However, contrary to the breast, the lung is a good microwave absorber. This is mainly due to the different composition: adipose tissue for the breast against highly blood-irradiated tissue for the lung which displays a conductivity 15 times larger than that of breast tissue at 1 GHz.

This makes the design of a microwave detection device challenging. Thus, in this contribution we investigated several parameters affecting the quality of a confocal image for the localization of pulmonary nodules such frequency band, nodule depth, and number of antennas. These are necessary to guide the design of a suitable antenna and microwave transmitter/receiver to be used in a VATS setup.

II. Material and methods

The effect of frequency band, nodule depth, and number of antennas on the confocal maps were investigated through numerical modelling using GprMax [5], [6] a Finite Difference Time Domain (FDTD) solver. A sphere with dielectric properties approximating those of a pulmonary nodule was used as target. This was embedded in a homogeneous material with properties taken to resemble those of lung tissue and a simplified model for a monostatic antenna was placed on top of the lung tissue. This antenna was moved in a regular grid as to mimic the real procedure that a surgeon would use to produce a microwave image during VATS and a numerical simulation was performed at every position.

The parameters investigated were the central frequency of the excitation signal (500 MHz to 5 GHz), the number of antennas positions (9, 16, or 25 on a regular square grid), and the depth of the target into the lung tissue (1 to 10 cm). The confocal microwave images were created by confocal imaging using a Delay and Sum (DAS) algorithm [7].

III. Results and discussion

Figure 1: Wavelength λ and attenuation α for an electromagnetic wave travelling in lung tissue.

The wavelength λ and attenuation α for the electromagnetic wave inside lung tissue is shown in Fig. 1. The wavelength varies between several centimeters to some 8 mm in the frequency range investigated (500 MHz – 5 GHz). However, it is almost a straight line (in linear coordinated) meaning that the lung tissue has very weak dispersive properties in this frequency range. On the other side the attenuation grows quickly beyond 1 GHz, which means that the electromagnetic waves cannot travel deeply into this tissue.

Fig. 2 shows the cross section of a typical confocal image simulated using an antenna grid of 5x5 and an electromagnetic pulse centered at 600 MHz. The expected position of the nodule, which was simulated by a sphere of tissue with 1 cm of diameter with different dielectric properties compared to the surrounding, lay at a depth of 8 cm and it is highlighted by a white circle.

Figure 2: Confocal map performed at 600 MHz with a tumor located at 8 cm of depth. The white circle indicates the expected position of the cancer.

The confocal map displays some darker areas in the region of the target which can be used to assert its position. However, these darker areas cover a portion of the confocal map which is larger than the simulated nodule. Also, some rings appear, these were produced by the fact that when the antenna was positioned directly on top of the target the reflected wave was much stronger than for all the other positions.

These rings did not appear in the confocal maps produced with signals at higher frequencies. However, given the

strong attenuation of the electromagnetic waves in the lung tissue at higher frequencies (see Fig. 1), also the contrast in the confocal images deteriorated.

The quality of the confocal images was asserted quantifying the ratio between the pixel intensity at the expected target position against the pixel intensity of the surrounding.

The main finding of this work was that the selection of the frequency band plays the most important role in the localization of a pulmonary nodule through microwave confocal imaging and that the best investigated operational frequency was 600 MHz. In these conditions even nodules located at a depth of up to 10 cm could be clearly distinguished in the confocal images.

IV. Conclusions

In this contribution, numerical simulations were used to investigate the effect of several parameters on the quality of microwave confocal imaging of lung tissue. It was found that it was only possible to locate a 1 cm nodule in the lung when operating below 2 GHz.

This represents an initial guideline to select a proper antenna design to perform microwave imaging of lung tissue. However, more refined analysis and experimental validation are necessary to establish at which extent and with what limits microwave confocal imaging could be employed in video-assisted thoracoscopic surgery.

AUTHOR'S STATEMENT

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REFERENCES

- [1] F. Bray, J. Ferlay, I. Soerjomataram, R. L. Siegel, L. A. Torre, and A. Jemal, 'Global cancer statistics 2018: GLOBOCAN estimates of incidence and mortality worldwide for 36 cancers in 185 countries', *CA. Cancer J. Clin.*, vol. 68, no. 6, Art. no. 6, 2018, doi: 10.3322/caac.21492.
- [2] R. L. Siegel, K. D. Miller, and A. Jemal, 'Cancer statistics, 2016', *CA. Cancer J. Clin.*, vol. 66, no. 1, Art. no. 1, 2016, doi: 10.3322/caac.21332.
- [3] D. Ost, A. M. Fein, and S. H. Feinsilver, 'The Solitary Pulmonary Nodule', *N. Engl. J. Med.*, vol. 348, no. 25, Art. no. 25, Jun. 2003, doi: 10.1056/NEJMcp012290.
- [4] E. C. Fear, X. Li, S. C. Hagness, and M. A. Stuchly, 'Confocal microwave imaging for breast cancer detection: localization of tumors in three dimensions', *IEEE Trans. Biomed. Eng.*, vol. 49, no. 8, Art. no. 8, Aug. 2002, doi: 10.1109/tbme.2002.800759.
- [5] A. Giannopoulos, 'Modelling ground penetrating radar by GprMax', *Constr. Build. Mater.*, vol. 19, no. 10, Art. no. 10, Dec. 2005, doi: 10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2005.06.007.
- [6] C. Warren, A. Giannopoulos, and I. Giannakis, 'gprMax: Open source software to simulate electromagnetic wave propagation for Ground Penetrating Radar', *Comput. Phys. Commun.*, vol. 209, pp. 163–170, Dec. 2016, doi: 10.1016/j.cpc.2016.08.020.
- [7] M. Elahi *et al.*, 'Evaluation of Image Reconstruction Algorithms for Confocal Microwave Imaging: Application to Patient Data', *Sensors*, vol. 18, no. 6, Art. no. 6, May 2018, doi: 10/ggppbd.